

How Service Industries Can Transform Themselves into Green Business Industries

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Abstract

Green business in service sector is expected to transform industrial economy to service economy and is complied with the trend of world economy development. Environmental benefits and sustainability are two characteristics of Green business. Under the background of the transformation of the world economic structure, what the companies provide to customers should be no longer the pure physical products, but more and more dematerialization services. For example, the companies provide services (or a function, effectiveness) to the customers as the complementation of physical products, which will prolong and strengthen the relationship between providers and customers, make the companies pay more attention to product life cycle cost management, stimulate the companies reducing the consumption of energy and the emission of greenhouse gases, improve the production efficiency and reduce cost. In the green business model, service is expanded to the main components of business model such as, what kinds of product and service will be provided by companies (the process of service creation), how will the product and service be transferred to customers, how will the benefits be captured by providers around service (value realization). In this paper, we have analysed and discussed how Service Industries can transform themselves into Green Business Industries in terms of their opportunities and challenges by considering 21 service sectors. The consequences of going green and sustainability of service sector by technology adoption is also discussed.

Keywords : *Green Business, Green business in service sector, Factors affecting green business. Impact of green business.*

I. INTRODUCTION

A service industry is made up of companies that primarily earn revenue through providing intangible products and services. Service industry companies are involved in retail, transport, distribution, food services, as well as other service-dominated businesses. Service sector constitute over 50% of GDP in low income countries and as their economies continue to develop with time, the importance of services in the economy also continues to grow [1]. The service economy is found to be key aspect of growth in both developing and developed countries. As a result, employment is increasing in this sector and more people are shifting from the agricultural sector to find work in the service economy. This job creation is particularly useful as often it provides employment for low skilled labour in the tourism and retail sectors, thus benefiting the poor in particular and representing an overall net increase in employment [1]. The service economy is most often consisting of Financial services like Banking and insurance, Advertising, Retail, Tourism, Transportation, Distribution, Food services, Hospitality and food services, Marketing, Entertainment and recreation, Mass communication & media, Health care, Electronic communication services, IT and ITES, Education, Public utilities, Real estate and leasing, Public administration and defence, Business support services, Professional, scientific and technical services, and social services. In service sector employment, people use time to deploy knowledge assets, collaboration assets, and process-engagement to improve productivity, effectiveness, potential of performance improvement and sustainability. Service industry involves in the function of providing various services to businesses as well as final consumers. Services may involve transport, distribution and sale of goods from producer to a consumer as may happen in wholesaling and retailing, or may involve the provision of a service, such as in entertainment. In service industry, even goods may be transformed in the process of providing a service, as in the case of restaurant industry or in equipment repairing business. However, the focus is on people interacting with people and serving the customer rather than transforming physical goods.

II. BUSINESS MODELS OF SERVICE INDUSTRIES

A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value, in economic, social, cultural, environment or other contexts. The process of business model construction is part of business strategy of organizations for business profit and long term sustainability. The business model in service industry is used for describing the main aspects of a business, including purpose, business process, target customers, offerings, organizational structures, strategies, infrastructure, sourcing, trading practices, culture, operational processes and policies. It also describes how to use its environment and technology effectively to make the business profitable and sustainable. Al-Debei and Avison (2010) [2] have developed a V⁴ Business Model Framework with four dimensions encapsulating sixteen elements called: Value Proposition, Value Architecture, Value Network, and Value Finance. The Value Proposition implies that a business model should include a description of the products/services an

organization offers, or will offer, along with their related information. It also depicts the value elements incorporated within the offering, as well as the nature of targeted market segment(s) along with their preferences. The Value Architecture implies a holistic structural design of an organization, including its technological architecture, organizational infrastructure, and their configurations. The Value Network depicts the inter-organization perspective towards the concept. The Value Finance provides information related to costing, pricing methods, and revenue structure.

Recently, Sangeet Paul Choudary (2013) [3] distinguished between two broad families of business models as linear business models called pipes and as networked business models called platforms. In the case of pipes, firms create goods and services, push them out and sell them to customers. The platforms do not just create and push stuff out and allows users to create and consume value. One of the examples of various business models used in service industry are Bricks and clicks business model in which a company integrates both offline (*bricks*) and online (*clicks*) presences. Recently, many firms started the opening-up of business models by outsourcing activities to specialized service providers. More and more companies also innovate by collaborating with external firms. Thus, service-based business models open potential beyond the exploitation of economies of scale and scope to the extent that companies team up to jointly seize emerging market opportunities. Servicizing, can be considered as an operation which satisfies customers' needs by selling the usability, functionality, "non tangible" side of the product rather than the artifact itself. Service innovation consists of methods, actions and movements of each individual involved. Services are, by definition, interactive, and they have tended almost naturally to organize their innovation activity around an interactive model, that is, one in which actors from different departments interact [4].

Green business model innovation is when a business changes part(s) of its business model and thereby both captures economic value and reduces the ecological footprint in a lifecycle perspective. Generally, it can be said that: (1) the more parts of a business model which are changed and have a green effect, and (2) the more profoundly a green change is taking place within the individual parts of the business model going from modification, redesign, alternatives, to creation –the greener the business model innovation is and the higher potential for creating radical eco-innovation. Characteristics of green business are environmental benefits and sustainability, complies with the trend of world economy development, i.e. transformation from industrial economy to service economy. Under the background of the transformation of the world economic structure, what the companies provide to customers should be no longer the pure physical products, but more and more dematerialization services. Namely, the companies provide services (or a function, effectiveness) to the customers as the complementation of physical products, which will prolong and strengthen the relationship between providers and customers, make the companies pay more attention to product life cycle cost management, stimulate the companies reducing the consumption of energy and the emission of greenhouse gases, improve the production efficiency and reduce cost.

III. Service Industries as Green Industries :

As service industries are getting more prominent in today and as we are transiting from industrial economy to service economy there is a requirement that the services provided are helping not just in the country's GDP but also preserving and supporting our earth in terms of being eco-friendly. So as we are in service economy there is greater need for the services to go more sustainable and green. Therefore the service sector in their objective of satisfying and engaging the customers also have to abide by the environmental standards and follow such practices of being green.

In the study by Ernst & Young, (EC, 2006) [5] the eco-industry is defined by the following activities in the economy:

- Air pollution control
- Waste water treatment
- Solid waste management & recycling
- Remediation & clean-up of soil & groundwater
- Noise and vibration control
- Recycled materials
- Renewable energy production
- Environmental monitoring and instrumentation
- Eco construction
- Private Environmental management
- Environmental research & development
- Water supply
- Nature protection
- General public administration

Eco friendly companies can utilise information communication technology (ICT) and e-business model more in their operations so that in giving better services to the customers there is sustainability benefit that can be an added value to

their services. The Eurostat publication “The environmental goods and services sector : A data collection handbook” (2009) [6] states that the environmental goods and service sector consists of a heterogeneous set of producers of technologies, goods and services that: measure, control, restore, prevent, treat, minimize, research and sensitize environmental damages to air, water and soil as well as problems related to waste, noise, biodiversity and landscapes. The implication of all this is that the services have to use the green technology that helps in preventing or minimizing pollution and measuring and preventing resources depletion. Resource efficient services will help in minimising the wastages of natural resources. Along with keeping all the stakeholders satisfied it’s also essential that the end purpose of every service organisation should be resource efficiency and environmental safeguard as the prime concern. Therefore all service organisations are following the green business model which incorporates green in all processes where the service is rendered. When firms do this they have to also focus on economic and social benefits also. The business model has to be unique and differentiated so that in the world of competition they stand out and also act as a role model to others by adding the component of green in the process of service creation, service operations and in service delivery.

(A) Opportunities to Go Green :

As per Briyan Titley, 2008 [8], “there are five key steps in each business life cycle i.e. inputs, process, outputs, environment externalities and marketing”. Green business houses to be successful should implement the cleaner green business practices and also be in a position to communicate about their business services to build up their brand and capture the market share for the green business practices that they have adopted. The strategies should be not just avoiding environmental harmful elements but also understand the life cycle of their services. Differentiation among the products and services are relatively same amongst all products and services. Therefore the green factor becomes an important feature that can be added to the services and make the consumers purchase the services. It is evident that along with price and quality consumers of today are looking for the green and there exists a huge demand for green services and businesses. Brand loyalty can also be established with this method.

Whenever the companies try to go green there is an increase in business reputation. It also leads to innovations and there is a savings in terms of costs which helps businesses to be more competitive. It’s known that it’s not just the customers who are demanding green, the employees also feel favourable to work in such organisations which are green. They will be more productive and indirectly will be very loyal to their organisation. This helps the firm in further saving costs in terms of hiring and training costs. The companies can also benefit in terms of lesser regulations because they abide by their standards. Whenever the companies do cause related marketing it helps them distinguish themselves in the cluttered market place and space.

(B) Challenges to Go Green :

As there are innumerable opportunities to go green so exists a huge set of challenges. Creating consumers trust is one of the biggest challenges. Explaining green is difficult. There are chances that consumers can think the claims made by marketing department is false claims and treat is as greenwash. This can damage the company’s credibility and hurt the brand and the company name for a number of years. There can also be legal risks associated with this and additional expenses that the company has to bear. The concept of green being technical and complex majority of the consumer may fail to understand it. This poses as a second challenge for the company. With this confusion the consumers may shift their purchasing to some competitor brand. The third challenge is that the competitors might copy the green strategy very quickly and easily and therefore the need to upgrade the green strategy is very essential. Clean climate, green resources are the issues that all the stakeholders will be interested in. The following service sectors have potential advantages to greening their processes directly or indirectly either by using technology or newer innovative green business models.

(1) Green Advertising:

It is essential to offer a different creative communication in a more ecological and socially sensitive way. Advertising services can be offered to companies that aim to highlight the competitive advantages of their products while enhancing environmental and social benefits. Products and companies associated with organic food, renewable energy, companies for environmental and social work etc is the major clients of such green advertising agencies. A wide range of above the line and below the line services are available which are purely green and do not harm the environment in any manner. Packaging is also one of the activities done by advertising agencies. The advertising agencies can give ideas to companies regarding product packaging where the environmental gains can be accomplished. Using refillable containers, paper vs. plastic and cardboard vs. Styrofoam will be more needed as this is an area of regulatory interest. The truth about an advertised environmental claim is likely an Internet search away or can be found on more of numerous environmental watchdog sites like greenwashingindex.com. Advertisers use sand, biodegradable chalk, water fountains and a number of other sustainable mediums to get their message out. The future

of the planet is kept in mind when they design advertisements. Hence opportunity in using digital media for advertising has tremendous potential in greening advertising services.

(2) Green Banking & Insurance :

Banking and insurance sectors are playing a very crucial role in propagating green by promoting sustainability. Environmental friendly internal bank processes, physical infrastructure and green products and services helps in reducing bad effect on the environment. With the right planning the financial sector is achieving the right strategies and tactics to go green. Banks invest or lend to businesses and projects which are environment friendly. This can set a movement for the companies to go green. They support such organisations which adopt green philosophy by giving fund to such organisations. The banks can also take the initiative to generate power in various places by setting up wind mills with collaboration with energy companies. Banks and insurance companies can initiate green channel by supporting paperless transaction in all the branches like cash withdrawal cash deposit, and fund transfers. Solar power ATM is also another way for the banks to go green. This in turn reduces the carbon emissions. Lots of green services are done by the banks in the form of green loans, green savings accounts, mobile banking, green credit cards, online transactions etc. Achieving a green excellence awards may be a motivation for banks and insurance companies to go ahead to be green.

(3) Green Retailing :

Green retailing is one more service industry that is going green in a massive way. The main areas that any retail organisation can go green are by incorporating the right green infrastructure and green supply chain management. The supply chain has to be redesigned and using sources of energy and alternate fuels for going green. This helps them to reduce costs by using lesser energies and using natural lightings. This also helps in controlling emissions. Solar, wind and green technology is used to operate the stores, equipments, vehicles and facilities. The retail stores can continuously improve in terms of operational level by controlling energy by using low energy lighting systems which uses more natural lights than artificial lights during day hours. Rooftop solar energy is also one option that helps in controlling energy and in turn benefits the organisation in terms of money and checks emissions. Green gives the benefits in terms of energy, water, and waste and carbon management. Using the right green technology in various processes of retail services supports green retailing.

(4) Green Tourism :

Tourism is one of the prominent service sectors which bring a lot of revenue to the country. It is the necessity of the hour to go green with respect to tourism sector as well. Green tourism should take into the aspects of economic, socio- cultural and environmental balance. Optimal use of environmental resources should play a key role in green tourism. It also comprises of conserving natural heritage of the country and biodiversity. To make tourism green it requires the support of all stakeholders. The visitors also have an obligation to keep the tourist places in utmost green way by not harming and deteriorating the environment. Green tourism requires continuous monitoring and regular measures either preventive or corrective measures need to be taken on a regular basis. It also involves maintaining a high level of customer satisfaction and giving a valuable experience to the tourists, increasing their awareness about sustainability and promoting green tourism.

(5) Green Transportation :

The transportation system has lots of negative effects and the concept of greening the transportation system is very crucial. There are many issues with the present transportation system. Along with the environmental effect that is caused by the vehicles, it also has issues such as bad road use practices, health problems both mental and physical either because of noise pollution and air pollution. Greening of the transportation system helps in reducing the carbon footprint which is the main cause of climate change or global warming. So global warming, health impacts and environmental damage are the crucial problems that need to be addressed. Transportation machines should be such that at producing, using or disposing of machines care should be taken by the companies that least negative impact can be assured.

The solutions to go green in transportation services are changing the vehicle types, using alternate fuels and wiser vehicle use. Shifting the automobile technology from petrol based fuel to renewable fuel. Transportation as a service uses information communication technology for online booking of vehicles, passenger seat reservation, vehicle tracking etc. to green the service.

(6) Green Distribution :

Distribution involves the coordination and management of a network of activities which involves delivering finished products to the final customer or consumer. Green distribution aims at eliminating or minimising waste of any type like emissions, energy or hazardous solid wastes along the supply chain. The solution is green procurement, green

distribution and green logistics. The 3 R's of reduce, reuse, recycle should be incorporated while purchasing. The selection of the supplier should be one who is satisfying environmental quality standards and a green partner. Green distribution comprises of green packaging and green logistics. Green packaging involves using downsize packaging, using green packaging materials and trying to minimise the materials to unpack and have a strategy that encourages and adopts returnable packaging materials which helps recycling and reuse initiatives. Green logistics includes delivering directly to user site, use alternative fuel vehicles and distribute products together rather than in smaller batches. It also includes online tracking of goods and packets, vehicle tracking using information communication technology to green the distribution service.

(7) Green Hospitality and food services,

Hoteliers have now the focus to the importance of sustainability in the hospitality industry as it is directly have an environmental and economic impact. Energy and water consumption, hazardous waste creations are the main objectives to be solved of going green. Hotels should conserve energy and use lesser energy in operations, lighting and other power needs. Water should be conserved minimal in bathrooms, laundry, food & beverages, cleaning and maintenance. Waste generated in the hotel should be reduced. Renewable sources of energy are used in today's day hospitality sector. The green concept is essential for multiple reasons. When the hotels go green the operating costs reduces. Sustainable procuring materials, indoor environment conditions which use nonhazardous chemical or cleaning products, water management are some of the strategies used by hotel industries to go green.

(8) Green Entertainment and recreation :

The consumers when they looking for entertainment and recreation services are also looking at green component when they make their purchasing choice. The objective is to lessen any adverse effects of recreations on natural environment. Healthy and sustainable recreation is what the consumers are looking for. The energy used to produce an event can be made sustainable by using solar systems or wind energy. The equipments used by the event management company and the recreation services should also be eco-friendly in nature. The resources such as supplies and materials to produce an event should be such that it has the least negative impact. Preserving the natural environment, the eco systems, flora and fauna are an essential challenge to the environmental management in entertainment companies.

(9) Green Mass communication & media :

Mass communication and media can adopt information and communication technology (ICT) for transmission of video & audio information. The various opportunities in mass communication and media are: promoting online E-Newspapers to decrease paper and ink usage and its consequence on environmental pollution can be minimized. Video conferencing using ICT to transmit information for TV channels, news agencies shall minimize transportation and contributes to the green environment. Digital advertisements replace advertisements in newspapers, magazines and posters which intern minimize the pollution and supports green environment. Online education, TV channel based education & online Training programmes decrease the physical material usage and also environmental degradation. Innovation in integrating mass communication, video camera, audio recording & hearing, and mobile applications in a single device leads to decrease in recycling of many electronic devices. The challenges include the latest technology adoption, training the people, cost, mindset to change.

(10) Green Health care Services :

Health care services are also in mode of going green with the rising innovation and technology. Health sector also targets sustainability as one of their objectives of service. They are also working towards minimizing the ill effects of environment and reducing the medical garbage. They identify the best plans, practices and utilise their operating rooms, general wards in such a manner that will help save energy consumption, medical waste. This in turn will lessen cost to the patients and will reduce patient and worker exposure to harmful chemicals. Energy consumption saving is also one of the ways by which hospitals can go green. Switching to energy efficient equipments is also one of the ways of green. Energy star rating by the various departments could make the sector still stronger in achieving sustainability. The challenge lies in investing a lot of money, time and ideas to help the hospitals to go green.

(11) Green Electronic communication services :

Green electronic communication services needs to be sustainable in today's competitive environment. There has been a substantial increase in the amount of information and communication that is stacked and transmitted electronically. Traditional paper documentation and papers is not popular and used in today's business world. Electronic communication provides benefits in terms of text, graphics, pictorial, audio and other forms that can be created and modified and distributed by a computer system. The tearing up and reprocessing of many of electronic documents can make any offices paper free and with that we can conserve our one of the best resources i.e. the forests. The

challenges are to see that system functions effectively with good policies and procedures and with sufficient training to the employees.

(12) Green IT and IT Enabled Services :

The business productivity and quality of life has risen because of Information technology (IT). This has resulted in the massive usage of IT services which in turn has burdened our environment in terms of depletion of fuel and other raw materials. The sector is reducing the power consumption of IT equipment, environmentally friendly buildings, e-cycling etc. Saving energy and fuel costs can help the firms to go green. This helps them to save costs also. The IT sector is using alternative energy sources, recycling; energy efficient lighting etc helps the company to be sustainable. By acquiring environmental certificates it helps them to get customer support also. The challenge is likely in creating the widespread awareness in adopting Green IT practices.

(13) Green Education

Education services are also working towards achieving green and being environmental friendly. Growth or learning will only take place in an environment which is conducive for development in children's life. Academicians, administrators, students need to incorporate awareness and adoption of environmental friendly practices in the learning process. The culture of conservation has to be an integral part of the curriculum. The tools and techniques along with eco-friendly building and equipments have to be used in teaching-learning process. The future generations should be able to understand and protect natural resources and in that process protect human health by being environmental initiators.

(14) Green Public utility services :

Green public utility services must consist of conserving resources in terms of rainwater, toxics, recycling and waste management, energy management, community welfare, water and waste water. Improvements and continuous recommendations are essential in these areas to go green. Green standards should be identified in these areas and opportunities for continuous achieving green standards should be the objective. Making lighting changes, reducing carbon footprint, upgrades with respect to heating and cooling and ventilation are some of the strategies adopted in public utility services. The challenge lies in investment and acceptance by all the stakeholders.

(15) Green Real estate and leasing :

Green buildings include recycled and abundant resources to create sustainable products that eliminate all toxic elements. Eco-friendly materials like recycled glass and sand and green technology can be used to reduce energy in construction phase.

The interiors of the building used by the builders contain impressive bio content which reduces the carbon footprint. There are also some eco- friendly adhesives and insulation products for the flooring. These green adhesives contain zero VOCs and solvents and contribute to LEED credits and they are sustainable in nature. There are products that are available that provides detailed consumption data for residential and commercial water users. Using thermal energy by green builders helps in reducing energy costs. The ecopower systems help in anticipating heating demand and runs at a level to maintain constant heat reducing energy costs. The technology reduces the carbon footprint substantially. Even roofs are energy conservative. The non-vegetated cooling controls that detain storm water which provides substantial benefits through rooftop cooling and reduce energy use in hot, sunny weather. Hence using green technology in various real estate projects and leasing processes will also deepen the greenness.

(16) Green Public administration :

Public administration is expected to be good example of incorporating green resources in their organisation's day to day operations. Governmental organisations have created policies to make sure that their operations have lessened environmental impact. Even without the formal policies individual public employees have to display pro-environmental behaviour and be eco-initiatives. Reducing the total amount of waste in all resources is one way in public administration that can make them green. Technology can be used to make office places paper less. Waste processes can be prevented or reduced through appropriate technology; this in turn will bring greenness in public administration. The challenges lie in acceptance of this by the general public.

(17) Green Defence Services :

In defence services energy is an essential element. Without energy the military operations cannot function. Green energy innovations are necessary so that the expenditure can be reduced. Lot of national initiatives have been undertaken so that there is cleaner, faster and sustainable and inexpensive ways to meet the needs of the defence forces of the country. Constant research of going green in equipments used is also one of the initiatives taken by the defence services. This helps the country as a large because of lesser budgets that can be allocated for defence. Solar

power can also be used at relevant places. The challenge lies in training the armed forces about this new system of giving services.

(18) Green Business support services :

Every business requires a lot of business support services in the form of maintenance, back end operations services and other allied services. There is a broad portfolio of services in this regard that has to be maintained green. The objective of all these services is to have least effect on the environment. Reduction in the greenhouse gas emissions should be the main focus here. The energy used by these services has to go green and any kind of transportation services should also be in such a way that they do not harm the environment in long run. Sufficient care should be taken with respect to the kind of equipments used to do the maintenance and other services required by their clients. Sufficient training is required so that we have the best support services which is not just ecologically beneficial but also cuts cost to the organisation.

(19) Green Marketing :

Green marketing is the concept of sustainable marketing and in the process keeping the profitability of the organisations. The objective of any green organization should be to satisfy and delight the customer in a manner that is not bad to the society or to planet at large. The firms should go beyond just the profitability element and satisfy the customers in such a way that the brand and the products create a positive and life time relationship with the company. Green marketing incorporates green brands that are green in the entire journey of the product or service i.e. the product life cycle from cradle to grave. Green marketing is the management process authorised for identifying, anticipating and satisfying the requirements of customers and society, in a profitable and sustainable way. Green marketing strategy focuses on three main actions: reducing, recycling and re-using resources. The service organisations should design green services and implement it in such a way that is helpful in achieving the bottom line profits. Fewer and efficient use of resources is one such way. With right segmentation, targeting and positioning strategies the green marketing done by service industries can achieve brand loyalty by the consumers.

(20) Professional, scientific and technical services :

There are a lot of services required by different businesses and individual customers in the form of professional services like lawyer services, architect, specialised engineering services etc. Scientific and technical services are used by organisations for research or some specific technical expertise like accounting or book keeping services, research services, etc. Certain services like consulting or photographic services are required by the final consumers in a larger scale. It's required that these services also need to be green and try to give their services in such a manner that has least effect to its environment. They also should emphasis on green by their energy usage and the resources efficiency. Fewer amounts of paper transactions are one approach that they can adopt. Utilising their expertise knowledge and innovation in their services can reach to maximum number of clients at lesser cost and keeping the approach of environment friendly. The greatest challenge these services have to face is training and research in the equipments they use.

(21) Social services :

Social service organisations also should be a role model to other organisations in their objective of giving social services with the greenness strategy. They are in fact required to be more following the principles of environment and ecology. Most of the social services organisations have green teams and they can help in creating the awareness and implementation of earth friendly approaches. They also install solar panels in their surrounding region so that energy can be conserved and they also are using recycled papers. They also can initiate programs with respect to green programs like collection and recycling cell phones and batteries. Certain digital initiatives can also be initiated in their nearby areas to cut down all paper waste. Programs such as raising awareness about recycle plastic bags and reusable bags are already done by most social service agencies. Water and power conservation strategies will benefit not just individuals or local community; it will benefit the state and the overall country. In this way they can set an example of being environmental leader along with being social service providers. The challenge is securing the support from the local community and getting the right funds and donations for their social service campaigns.

IV. CONSEQUENCES OF GO GREEN MODEL FOR SERVICE INDUSTRIES

The following are the consequences of go green model in service sector which helps business sustainability :

- (1) Improvement in service quality
- (2) Decrease in service expenditure
- (3) Use of latest technology in service industry to incorporate service processes green/pollution free
- (4) Minimizing service time & waiting time
- (5) Decreasing the hidden cost in availing the service

- (6) Online & Ubiquitous service availability
- (7) Customer expectation
- (8) Customer satisfaction & Delight
- (9) Environmental sustainability
- (10) Decreased contribution to environmental degradation & climate change
- (11) Contribution to economy
- (12) Improved human relations & Eradication of poverty
- (13) Enhanced awareness in environment & sustainability

Use of green technologies in agriculture, water purification & supply, energy sector, health sector services leads to permanent solution to long time problems in developing countries.

V. GO GREEN CONCEPT AND SUSTAINABILITY

In the green business model, this value proposition concept is not framed or named as such but the analysis can be translated from the discussion on the economic and social benefits. Sustainability is an important parameter in deciding the effectiveness and quality of any service in terms of economic and social benefits. Any service which uses and supports green concepts by reducing environmental de-gradation is considered to be sustainable. The Concept of Sustainability examines three aspects of sustainability – the environment, society and the economy. Any Business service which takes care of sustainable clean environment without leaving its footprint, which does not contribute to the social problems and which contribute to the economical development the country is regarded as green. Most of the service industries can plan their service strategies environmental friendly by adopting green technologies for sustainability.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have analysed and discussed how Service Industries can transform themselves into Green Business Industries in terms of their opportunities and challenges by considering 21 service sectors which include Green Advertising, Green Banking & Insurance, Green Retailing, Green Tourism, Green Transportation, Green Distribution, Green Hospitality and food services, Green Entertainment and recreation, Green Mass communication & media, Green Health care Services, Green Electronic communication services, Green IT and IT Enabled Services, Green Education, Green Public utility services, Green Real estate and leasing, Green Public administration, Green Defence Services, Green Business support services, Green Marketing, Professional, scientific and technical services, Social services. The consequences of going green and sustainability of service sector by technology adoption is also discussed. It is believed that the green business adopting green products and green services are going to be sustainable due to their ability to maintain clean and sustainable environment.

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